

Curvature and Probability of Arrival

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial coupling constants series and the main equation, it is possible to correlate the feature of the probability of the different classes of spin, to curvature and so eventually to probability. The paper is an elaboration on the previous subject that analyzed only the probability of arrival for boson due to their net curvature unbound. The paper than will refer to fermions as well.

Introduction

The 8-theory regard fermions as arbitrary variations of a manifold, which vanish into matter.

$$\left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \right] \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \left[\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \right] \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0$$

$$\delta g_1 \rightarrow (+) \quad (1.1)$$

$$\delta g_2 \rightarrow (-) \quad (1.11)$$

Such a construction allowed us to build an infinite series of two distinct elements that differ in sign. By allowing each element to vary, we proved they create nine threefold combinations, or vanish into matter, similar to the group proven by Gell Mann in the 60's. The result is no curvature on the varying (3,1) connected manifold, which was invoked stationary. Such a construction also support the charge conjugation and symmetry under sign reversal as the series would still vanish into zero ensuring a stationary Lorentzian.

$$\delta g_1 \rightarrow (-) \quad (1.18)$$

$$\delta g_2 \rightarrow (+) \quad (1.19)$$

The physical meaning of that construction is that the existence of fermions or matter at certain spatial dimension on the manifold would not affect the probability of arrival for additional matter to the same point as curvature is not allowed and does not exist at that point.

That is not the case for bosons, which are regarded as net curvature on the manifold. Curvature unbound which is isomorphic to prime numbers or one, and given by primorial coupling constants series.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.2)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.21)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.3)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.31)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.32)$$

Alternatively, in spin representation:

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_1 + 1$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_2 + 1$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} = 2N_3 + 1$$

Each boson is net curvature on the manifold, and thus increase the probability of arrival for other bosons to its spatial position. That is the underlining reason for their behavior and high probability of arrival. That is the difference among fermions and bosons. In this framework is vividly clear.

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \gamma_i = \sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.33)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)
- [2] O. Manor. "Proving Einstein Wrong about Gravity" In: (2021)